

UHPLC-MS/MS analysis of PFAS in the serum of patients with Alzheimer's disease, mild cognitive impairment and controls: A preliminary study

O. Deda^{a,b,1,*}, S. Adams^{c,1,2}, M. Tsolaki^{d,e,f}, A. Lioupi^a, A.C. Tsolaki^{e,f},
G. Theodoridis^{a,g}, I.D. Wilson^h, R.S. Plumbⁱ, H. Gika^{a,b,*}

^a Biomic AUTH, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI-AUTH), Balkan Center B1.4, 10th km Thessaloniki-Thermi Rd., P.O. Box 8318, Thessaloniki 57001, Greece

^b Department of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki 54124, Greece

^c Waters Corporation, Stamford Avenue, Wilmslow, SK9 4AX, UK

^d 1st Department of Neurology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki 54124, Greece

^e LND, AUTH, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI-AUTH), Balkan Center B1.4, 10th km Thessaloniki-Thermi Rd., P.O. Box 8318, Thessaloniki 57001, Greece

^f Alzheimer Hellas, Thessaloniki, Greece

^g Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

^h Division of Systems Medicine, Department of Metabolism, Digestion and Reproduction, Imperial College London, Hammersmith Campus, London W12 0NN, United Kingdom

ⁱ Research, Development & Advanced Testing Business, Waters Corporation, Milford, Massachusetts, 01757, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ultra short chain PFAS
Long chain PFAS
Screening
UHPLC-MS/MS
Exposomics
Exposure

ABSTRACT

Complimentary UHPLC-MS methods for 6 ultra short chain (polar) and 30 long chain (and relatively non-polar) PFAS compounds have been developed and used to profile these compounds in human serum. The methods were developed to be rapid, with both having analysis times of ca. 5 min, to enable the rapid screening of samples. Both methods were sensitive enough to detect the target PFAS over the range 0.5–50 ng/mL. These methods were then applied to the screening of the serum of 137 subjects comprising healthy controls (HC), subjects with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and those with Alzheimer's disease (AD). These methods demonstrated the presence of the 33 of targeted PFAS in these serum samples, presenting over a wide concentrations range with PFPrA found at the highest maximum concentration of 707 ng/mL. Interestingly the PFAS profiles found for the HC and MCI subjects differed from those of the AD patients. The reason(s) for differences in the PFAS profiles obtained for serum from AD patients compared to HC/MCI subjects is unclear and may be unrelated to disease but clearly warrants further investigation to clarify the underlying reasons for this observation.

1. Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are widely utilized in industrial and consumer products. Notably, perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS), known as legacy PFAS, have a structure containing 8-carbon atoms (C8) and have been used extensively since the 1940s [1]. Due to their environmental persistence, bioaccumulation, and toxicity to wildlife, animals and humans, their production and use have been increasingly regulated over the last two decades [1].

Large-scale biomonitoring initiatives, including the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) led by the CDC in the United States [2], the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) covering 30 European countries [3,4], the Canadian Health Measures Survey (CHMS) [5], the Australian National PFAS Management Program [6], and the Flemish Environment and Health Study (FLEHS) in Belgium [7], are pivotal frameworks for evaluating worldwide trends in exposure to PFAS. The main goals of these initiatives are to pinpoint sources of PFAS contamination, monitor exposure trends over time and understand what, if any, the potential impacts of these

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: olgadeda@auth.gr (O. Deda), gkikae@auth.gr (H. Gika).

¹ authors of equal contribution.

² present address. Fera Science Ltd., Sand Hutton, York YO41 1LZ, UK.

persistent environmental pollutants are and then mitigate the risks to human health posed by these substances.

Regulation has led to the use of shorter-chain PFAS, believed to be less persistent and bio-accumulative [8,9]. However, recent studies show that these compounds are also now widespread in environments such as dust, air, water, soil, and sediments. Due to their persistence and mobility, they are classified as substances of very high concern under the EU REACH program, prompting calls for urgent regulation [10].

In the context of human health there is also emerging evidence for the potential effects of PFAS and there is increasing interest in determining if there are any links to disease resulting from exposure to them. Relation with neurodegenerative disease has been a topic of interest and it was shown that PFAS cross the blood brain barrier [11,12], from both *in vitro* and [13] *in vivo* studies in mice [14] as well as in neurological conditions including Alzheimer's disease (AD) [15].

Due to the ever-increasing interest for the accurate determination of PFAS in studies of human biomonitoring and exposure estimation, there is a need for rapid and sensitive methods to facilitate the unambiguous quantification of such pollutants in biological samples, in particular short-chain PFAS which have been so far somewhat overlooked.

Here we describe the application of two complementary UHPLC-MS/MS methods suitable for the rapid screening of human serum, one for the analysis of 30 long-chain PFAS and a second method optimized for the analysis of a further 6 short-chain PFAS species. These combined methods enabled several PFAS molecules to be quantified for the first time in the serum of Alzheimer (AD) patients. The results presented here constitute a preliminary study performed evaluate the suitability of the developed methods to assess the PFAS exposure in the general population, rather than e.g., workers in those industries where high exposure is likely. We chose to investigate serum from 137 subjects, comprising healthy controls (HC) and two sets of neurological patients, either showing symptoms of Alzheimer's disease (AD) or mild cognitive impairment (MCI).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and materials

LC-MS grade acetonitrile (ACN) and methanol (MeOH) were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Loughborough, UK). De-ionized water was obtained by using a Purelab Chorus system from Elga (High Wycombe, UK). Ammonium acetate (AF) was purchased from Waters (Wilmslow, UK) and anhydrous sodium hydroxide, Optima LC/MS grade formic acid and ammonium hydroxide, 28–30 % (v/v Aq) from Fisher Scientific (Loughborough, UK). All Analytical standards of PFAS, native mix PFAC-30PAR, internal standard mixes MPFAC-24ES and MPFAC-C-IS, individual (native standards, ultra-short chain PFAS) TFA, PFPrA, PFMS (TFMS), PFETs and PFPrS and individual stable isotope-labelled standard M3-HFPODA, were purchased from Greyhound Chromatography (Birkenhead, UK), the UK supplier of Wellington Standards.

The standard reference materials (SRM) NIST 1957 serum was obtained from Merck Life Science UK Limited (Gillingham, UK).

2.2. Samples

A total of 137 serum samples were collected from two Day Centers, specifically, the 3rd Department of Neurology of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and Alzheimer Hellas of the Greek Association of Alzheimer's Disease and Related Disorders, during routine neurological visits. These included samples from patients and control subjects. The study was approved under protocol number 83/23-11-2022.

These samples included patients diagnosed for AD ($n = 75$), mild cognitive impairment (MCI) ($n = 40$) or no diagnosed mental illness (healthy controls, $n = 22$). The sample set comprised both male ($n = 61$) and female ($n = 76$) of ages from 18 to 87 years old [16]. The standard reference material (SRM) NIST 1957 human serum was used as a

reference sample for the method.

2.3. Sample preparation

The sample preparation protocol outlined in this study was designed to ensure precise and reproducible results in the quantification of the target analytes. For the calibration curve, stock solutions were prepared as follows: The stock solution concentration of PFAC-30PAR was 1000 ng/mL, with dilutions prepared at 100 ng/mL and 10 ng/mL, respectively. Stock solutions of TFA, PFPrA, TFMS, PFETs and PFPrS were combined to give a mixture with a concentration of 1000 ng/mL of each PFAS standard. Dilutions were prepared at 100 ng/mL and 10 ng/mL in MeOH. An internal standard (IS) extraction standard spiking mixture, used for recovery correction, was prepared at a final concentration of 5 ng/mL. This involved diluting M3-HFPODA stock solution to 1000 ng/mL and creating a mixture of MPFAC-24ES and M3-HFPODA at concentrations of 100 ng/mL and 10 ng/mL. The injection solution contained 8 mM aqueous ammonium acetate in water, supplemented with 2 ng/mL of MPFAC-C-IS (used as an internal injection standard), while the calibration dilution solution was maintained at the same ammonium acetate concentration, supplemented with 2 ng/mL of IS extraction standard spiking mixture and 2 ng/mL of MPFAC-C-IS. To prepare the extraction solutions, the following final concentrations were used: 1 % formic acid in ACN, 1:3 (v/v) ACN:H₂O, 2 % (v/v) ammonium hydroxide in methanol, 1 % formic acid in water, and 1 M ammonium acetate. The solutions with formic acid and ammonium hydroxide were prepared fresh on the day of extraction. The ACN/H₂O mixture had a shelf life of 7 days, and the ammonium acetate solution had a shelf life of 3 days.

For sample processing 50 μ L aliquots of serum (or water for blanks) were spiked with 20 μ L of the 10 ng/mL IS extraction standard mixture, followed by the addition of 150 μ L of 1 % formic acid in ACN. The samples were then mixed and centrifuged at 6000 xg. The resulting supernatant layer was mixed with 800 μ L of 1 % formic acid in water. The samples were then subjected to SPE clean-up using an Oasis WAX 96-well μ Elution plate containing 2 mg of sorbent per well. This method involved conditioning the SPE plate with 200 μ L of 2 % (v/v) ammonium hydroxide in MeOH, 200 μ L of MeOH and 200 μ L of 1 % formic acid in water. The sample was loaded onto the SPE cartridge in two aliquots of 500 μ L each, followed by washing with 200 μ L of 1 % formic acid in H₂O water and 200 μ L of ACN: H₂O water 1:3 (v/v). The samples were eluted with 50 μ L of MeOH, followed by 100 μ L of 2 % ammonia/MeOH (v/v) in two aliquots of 50 μ L each. The samples were then diluted with 50 μ L of 8 mM ammonium acetate (aq) containing internal injection standards. Samples contained within the 96 well plate were stored at -20°C until analysis.

Calibration standards were prepared directly on the 96-well plate, covering a range of concentrations to create a calibration curve for the quantification of target analytes over the range 0.125–12.5 ng/mL. As samples were diluted four times before injection, the concentration in the sample was calculated by multiplying with four. Solvent blanks were prepared by pipetting 50 μ L of MeOH, 100 μ L of 2 % ammonia: MeOH (v/v), and 50 μ L of injection solution, with at least 2 solvent blanks prepared for the analysis.

All solvents and reagents were screened prior to use in the study to identify potential sources of PFAs contamination. Only reagents that had been identified to be clear of contamination were used in the study. Trifluoroacetic acid had to be removed from the results due to contamination problems from solvents, where a clean source could not be identified.

2.4. UHPLC-MS/MS analysis

The samples were split into two batches with each batch of samples running on the PFAC 30PAR Mix method and Ultra Short Chain PFAS method respectively. Each batch of samples was run with 3 calibration brackets, one at the start of the run, the middle point of the batch and at

the end of the run. Associated extraction blanks and instrument system clear checks were run after the first two calibration brackets. Samples were run sequentially. NIST 1957 samples were also run with both batches.

All solvents and reagents to be used in the liquid chromatography method were screened prior to use in the study to identify potential sources of PFAS contamination. In addition the ACQUITY™ Premier UPLC™ chromatography system used had a PFAS Solution Installation kit (Waters Corporation, Milford, US) fitted. This kit replaces solvent and wash lines with PEEK tubing to reduce sources of PFAS contamination from the liquid chromatography system as well as an isolator column, an Atlantis Premier BEH C18 AX (50 × 2.1 mm I.D., 5 μm) (Waters), that delays potential contaminants coming from the system preventing them from interfering with the analyte peaks.

2.4.1. UHPLC of long chain (PFAC 30 PAR mix)

The analysis of the 30 long chain PFAS (optimized for the PFAC 30 PAR Mix) was performed on an ACQUITY™ Premier UPLC™ chromatography system (Waters Corporation, Milford, USA) comprising of an autosampler (ACQUITY Premier, FTN) and a binary solvent pump (ACQUITY Premier, BSM) and a column manager (ACQUITY Premier, CM). Analysis was conducted on a ACQUITY Premier HSS T3 (1.8 μm) 50 × 2.1 mm I.D., column (Waters). The mobile phases used for all sample analysis were 2 mM ammonium acetate in 95:5 H₂O/MeOH v/v (A) and 2 mM ammonium acetate in MeOH (B).

For the analysis of the 30 representative PFAS the following gradient program was employed. The initial mobile phase composition was maintained at 100 % A from 0 to 0.25 min then increased to 20 % B at 0.25 min, 45 % B at 1.5 min, 80 % B at 3.25 min, and 95 % B at 3.5 min this composition was maintained until 4.25 min. The mobile phase composition was then returned to 100 % A at 4.5 min and maintained at this composition until the next injection at 5.5 min. All UHPLC-MS/MS analyses were performed on 1 μL injections of sample.

2.4.2. UHPLC of ultra short chain PFAS

Ultra short chain PFAS analysis was conducted on an Atlantis Premier BEH C18 AX (50 × 2.1 I.D., 1.7 μm) (Waters). The mobile phases consisted of 2 mM ammonium acetate (95/5 H₂O: MeOH) (A) and 0.035 % ammonium hydroxide in MeOH (B). For the analysis of the ultra-short chain PFAS a multi-step gradient was used. The column was held at the initial composition of 99 % A for 0.5 min then increased to 25 % B at 0.75 min 50 % B at 2 min, before being steadily increased to 85 % B at 3.75 min, and 100 % B at 4 min, this composition was maintained until 5 min, when the organic composition was reduced to 100 % A at 5.03 min this was maintained until 5.88 min, then returned to the initial starting conditions of 99 % A at 6 min. All LC-MS/MS analyses were performed by injecting 1 μL of sample.

2.4.3. Tandem quadrupole mass spectrometry (MS/MS)

The column effluent was monitored using a Xevo™ TQ Absolute (Waters Corp, Wilmslow, UK) tandem quadrupole mass spectrometer operated in negative ESI using multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode. A capillary voltage of 0.5 kV was employed for all analytes, the desolvation temperature was set at 350 °C, desolvation, cone and nebulizer gas flow were set at 900, 150 and 150 L/h respectively. Cone voltage and collision energies were analyte dependent and are listed in the supplementary material (Table S1). Source temperature was set to 100 °C.

The MS dwell times ranged from 6 to 80 ms, set using an automatic parameter option and argon as collision gas at a pressure of 0.15 bar. The scan and peak widths were set at m/z 0.3 and m/z 0.7 respectively. The MRM transitions selected for the determination of the analytes, including internal standard used, quantifier and qualifier transition are listed in the supplementary material (Table S1). MassLynx v4.2 software was used to control the instrument setup, and data acquisition, with TargetLynx XS v4.2 software used for post run data processing.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analytical methods performance

Whilst, as noted in Materials and methods procedures can be put in place to minimize contamination issues remain. A significant problem when developing methods for widespread pollutants such as PFAS is that of obtaining blank matrices with which to prepare standard curves and others. Surrogate matrices are sometimes advocated as an alternative however, preparing a surrogate matrix for a complex biofluid such as serum, that accurately reflects the composition of real samples, is fraught with problems. To overcome this problem, we therefore used stable isotopically labelled internal standards in these methods to adjust not only for recovery correction in samples but also to correct for matrix effects during the LC-MS/MS analysis of human serum samples and used PFAS-free solvents to construct standard curves etc.

The methods were evaluated on multiple levels with the performance of the extracted internal standard being a critical parameter. Recoveries of the internal standards were measured against the response of the extracted internal standard in the calibration standards, adjusted by injection internal standards as a means to account for matrix suppression to give a more precise measure of recovery. As indicated above, the use of extracted internal standards present in the samples gives a means of both recovery correction and compensation for matrix suppression in the method. In Fig. S1 the range of recoveries observed are illustrated. Results from the NIST1957 sample ($n = 5$) are presented in Fig. S2 and relative recovery rates were, 121 to 144 % of the assigned value, with RSDs between 4 and 10 %, which was considered suitable for the purposes of this exploratory study (and within most contamination analysis methods range of method uncertainty, which is quoted as 50 %). The exception was PFUnDA which gave a relative recovery rate of 289 % and the results were treated as screen (with no residues being detected).

The ranges selected for the calibration curves in this preliminary study were based on publications [17,18] showing PFOS and PFOA concentrations in blood of the general population ~1–4 ng/mL with PFHxS detected at ~1–2 ng/mL. The higher percentiles (top 5 %) reached ~6–8 ng/mL for PFOS. Whilst occupational exposures may result in much higher (10–100 times) exposures this was not expected for the population studied here and the range employed was from 0.125 to 12.5 ng/mL (corresponding to 0.5 to 50 ng/mL when 4 the fold sample dilution for sample analysis is taken into account).

However, as reported below, a number of subjects exhibited higher values for some of the PFAS species. In addition, some PFAS were detected at concentrations below the LOQ but were still clearly present and have therefore been reported as detected. Whilst the concentrations of these analytes cannot be provided with any confidence the results for these PFAS they do, nevertheless, provide an indication of their presence and we have considered them in our discussion.

As can be seen, all the calibration curves were linear from 0.125 to 12.5 ng/mL, with residuals <20 % and coefficients of determination 0.99 or greater. Example calibration graphs of PFPrA, PFOA, PFHxS and PFOS are presented in Fig. S3. The method Limit of Quantification (LOQ) is quoted as 0.125 ng/mL based on the lowest calibration standard analyzed where the signal to noise was 10 to 1 or higher. All results were included in the statistical calculations, including results below the method LOQ but higher than the LOD where the S/N was 1/10 or greater and the analyte confirmed by ion ratio. Residues of PFAS were identified according to the following criteria, the relative retention time (RRT) was within ± 1 % of the average of the calibration standard results, the ion ratio of the qualifier ion/quantifier ion was within ± 30 % of the corresponding ion ratio of the reference standard. The signal to noise for the quantifier transition must also have been 10 to 1 or higher. Fig. S4 demonstrates method selectivity for PFAS residues detected in the study and from the NIST 1957 reference sample.

3.2. Application to control and clinical serum samples

3.2.1. PFAS exposure of the study population – General considerations

The derived sample data for the whole study population showed that the majority of the PFAS species analyzed (see **Table S1** for abbreviations and full names) were detected. However, whilst a sub-set of them could be quantified using the methods employed here, many were present only at trace concentrations in the serum samples (see data summary in **Table S2**). Nevertheless, several clear trends emerged from these data thus, PFBA was detected in all samples, while five PFAS (PFNA, PFOA, L-PFHxS, L-PFOS and br-PFOS) were observed in more than 90 % of the samples. Other frequently detected PFAS species included PFDA, PFHpA, PFPrA, PFHpS, and PFUnDA which were found in more than half of the samples. Conversely, eleven PFAS species (PFEtS, PFPeA, PFDoDA, PFDS, ADONA, 11CIPF3OUdS, 6_2 FTS, FBSA, FHxSA, FOSA and NEtFOSAA) were detected in less than 10 % of the analyzed the serum samples. Notably, three of the monitored PFAS species, namely PFTriDA, GenX, and 8:2 FTS were not detected in any of the samples.

These data are displayed in **Fig. 1** which shows the detection frequency of the different PFAS species analyzed by these methods in the studied samples, highlighting those PFAS with higher prevalence.

Regarding the extent of exposure of the subjects based on the concentrations measured it was found that PFPrA was in the highest mean concentration of 29.7 ng/mL (Median 7.2 ng/mL, ↓CI 15.3, ↑CI 44.7), followed by PFOA at an average of 5.0 ng/mL, l-PFOS at 2.5 ng/mL and Br-PFOS at 1.6 ng/mL. PFPrA is not within the analyte list of common PFAS analysis protocols due to poor retention and peak shape on a

reversed-phase LC column and most methods are designed for the analysis of PFAS with a longer carbon chain. Our finding is in agreement with recent reports indicating high PRPrA concentrations in environmental and biological samples [1], and the notably elevated levels observed in our cohort, further support its role as a major contributor to overall PFAS exposure.

The results shown in **Table 1** provide the maximum concentrations of the different PFAS species detected across all analyzed samples and give a clear picture of the highest concentrations of the PFAS present in the serum samples of the different subjects. PFPrA exhibited the highest maximum concentration at 707 ng/mL, significantly higher than all other PFAS species. PFOA followed with a maximum concentration of 529 ng/mL. PFNA and total PFOS (both linear and branched) had notable concentrations at 137 ng/mL and 17.8 ng/mL, respectively. In a few cases where such high concentrations were found, the determination might not be accurate as they fell outside the calibration range but are nevertheless reported as they provide an interesting perspective on individual exposures for future studies on these populations. Several other PFAS species, such as PFHpA, PFBA, L-PFOS, br-PFOS and 6:2 FTS, showed moderate maximum concentrations ranging from 7.0 ng/mL to 12.7 ng/mL. TFMS, total PFHxS, and L-PFHxS had maximum concentrations of between 4.1 ng/mL and 5.8 ng/mL, indicating their presence in relatively lower, but still measurable, amounts. Many PFAS species, including PFDA, PFUnDA, 9CIPF3ONS, NMeFOSAA and PFHpS, were only detected at maximum concentrations below 1.0 ng/mL.

Summing the combined amounts of all of the PFAS species found per individual, the range of sum PFAS concentrations were between 0 and 1037 ng/mL with an average of 48.1 ng/mL, a median of 26.8 ng/mL

Fig. 1. Percentage of detection observed in the analyzed serum samples from the examined population. Six of the species were found in more than 90 % of the population, indicating their widespread prevalence.

Table 1

Median values and average concentrations (µg/L), standard deviation, min, max, upper, and lower bound of 95 % Confidence Interval (CI) and percentage detection for all the subjects and median and p values for the three different groups and pair comparisons.

* Bold values denote either Total PFAS (summary) or p < 0.01. In the “% detected” column, percentages are in bold and the accompanying green bar represents detection frequency.

	median									pvalue				percent detection				
	median	average	std	CI	CI Low	CI High	min	max	HC	MCI	AD	MCI-HC	AD-MCI	AD-HC	All	HC	MCI	AD
PFPrA	7.24	29.75	86.00	14.40	15.35	44.16	0.00	706.52	23.06	25.98	3.64	0.58	0.19	0.13	80.3%	100%	100%	64%
TFMS	0.00	0.12	0.53	0.09	0.03	0.21	0.00	5.80	0.08	0.12	0.00	<0.01	0.30	0.80	42.3%	77.3%	92.5%	5.3%
PFETS	0.00	0.05	0.38	0.06	-0.01	0.12	0.00	3.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.39	0.43	8.8%	4.5%	17.5%	5.3%
PFPrS	0.00	0.04	0.18	0.03	0.01	0.07	0.00	2.04	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.13	0.12	0.18	46%	0%	10%	78.7%
PFBA	0.20	0.38	1.09	0.18	0.19	0.56	0.05	9.28	0.09	0.09	0.24	0.81	0.07	0.16	100%	100%	100%	100%
PFPeA	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.47	0.88	1.5%	4.5%	0%	1.3%
PFHxA	0.00	0.06	0.09	0.01	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.46	<0.01	<0.01	32.1%	0%	2.5%	57.3%
PFHpA	0.03	0.27	1.07	0.18	0.09	0.45	0.00	12.48	0.01	0.01	0.32	0.76	0.04	0.13	81.8%	72.7%	70%	90.7%
PFOA	0.68	4.96	45.13	7.56	-2.60	12.51	0.00	529.16	0.44	0.43	1.24	0.59	0.40	0.53	95.6%	95.5%	97.5%	94.7%
PFNA	0.56	1.63	11.64	1.95	-0.32	3.58	0.00	136.76	0.27	0.30	0.92	0.28	0.33	0.47	96.4%	95.5%	97.5%	96%
PFDA	0.21	0.40	0.36	0.06	0.34	0.46	0.00	1.28	0.17	0.16	0.72	0.83	<0.01	<0.01	83.2%	90.9%	90%	77.3%
PFUnDA	0.15	0.20	0.22	0.04	0.16	0.23	0.00	0.92	0.15	0.14	0.15	0.15	<0.01	0.05	59.9%	81.8%	65%	50.7%
PFDoDA	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.77	0.05	0.06	2.2%	4.5%	5%	0%
PFTriDA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0%	0%	0%	0%
PFTreDA	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.46	0.17	1.00	0.7%	0%	2.5%	0%
PFBS	0.00	0.03	0.08	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.29	<0.01	<0.01	18.2%	0%	5%	30.7%
PFPeS	0.00	0.04	0.12	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.00	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	<0.01	0.03	10.2%	0%	0%	18.7%
L-PFHxS	0.28	0.63	0.89	0.15	0.48	0.78	0.00	4.08	0.15	0.19	0.68	0.41	<0.01	<0.01	92%	95.5%	97.5%	88%
br-PFHxS	0.00	0.04	0.11	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.00	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	<0.01	<0.01	13.9%	0%	0%	25.3%

	median									pvalue				percent detection				
	median	average	std	CI	CI Low	CI High	min	max	HC	MCI	AD	MCI-HC	AD-MCI	AD-HC	All	HC	MCI	AD
Total PFHxS	0.28	0.67	0.98	0.16	0.51	0.84	0.00	4.44	0.15	0.19	0.68	0.41	<0.01	<0.01	92%	95.5%	97.5%	88%
PFHpS	0.07	0.24	0.24	0.04	0.19	0.28	0.00	0.72	0.03	0.03	0.44	0.80	<0.01	<0.01	80.3%	77.3%	80%	81.3%
L-PFOS	1.80	2.52	2.31	0.39	2.13	2.90	0.00	9.12	1.54	1.44	2.60	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	91.2%	95.5%	97.5%	86.7%
br-PFOS	0.99	1.57	1.82	0.31	1.26	1.87	0.00	8.64	0.55	0.71	1.68	0.51	<0.01	<0.01	91.2%	95.5%	97.5%	86.7%
Total PFOS	2.81	4.09	4.01	0.67	3.41	4.76	0.00	17.76	2.10	2.25	4.28	0.96	<0.01	<0.01	91.2%	95.5%	97.5%	86.7%
PFNS	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18	1.00	0.06	0.7%	4.5%	0%	0%
PFDS	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.56	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.30	0.90	2.2%	4.5%	0%	2.7%
GenX	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0%	0%	0%	0%
ADONA	0.00	0.01	0.08	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.10	0.22	3.6%	0%	0%	6.7%
9CIPF3ONS	0.00	0.18	0.28	0.05	0.13	0.23	0.00	0.76	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.81	<0.01	<0.01	45.3%	50%	45%	44%
11CIPF3OUdS	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.75	0.02	0.11	5.8%	9.1%	12.5%	1.3%
4_2 FTS	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.46	0.17	1.00	0.7%	0%	2.5%	0%
6_2 FTS	0.00	0.05	0.59	0.10	-0.05	0.15	0.00	6.96	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.47	0.59	1.5%	0%	0%	2.7%
8_2 FTS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0%	0%	0%	0%
FBSA	0.00	0.02	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.10	0.22	3.6%	0%	0%	6.7%
FHxSA	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.30	0.44	1.5%	0%	0%	2.7%
FOSA	0.00	0.02	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.83	0.36	0.43	6.6%	4.5%	7.5%	6.7%
NMeFOSAA	0.00	0.06	0.18	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.00	0.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.70	0.05	0.19	11.7%	9.1%	5%	16%
NEFOSAA	0.00	0.04	0.14	0.02	0.02	0.07	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.01	0.09	8.8%	4.5%	0%	14.7%

and Confidence Intervals of 28.4 \downarrow CI and \uparrow CI 67.8.

The exposure contribution of the individual PFAS was calculated by comparing the concentration of the individual PFAS to that of the sum of the total PFAS exposure. The highest contribution was from PFPrA (54 % of the total) followed by PFOS both linear (12 %) and branched (8 %). PFPrA was detected in 80 % of the population, The linear PFOS and branched PFOA were detected in 91 %, and 96 % of the subjects respectively. The mean PFPrA concentration accounted for more than half of the PFAS exposure.

These findings are depicted in the form of a pie chart (Fig. 2) that shows the mean percentage of PFAS species regarding the sum exposure to all measured species. As mentioned PFPrA accounted for more than half of the exposure, whilst 8 further PFAS between them accounted for circa 38 % of the total. Linear PFOS (L-PFOS) and branched PFOS (br-PFOS) also made up substantial portions of the total, accounting for 12.1 % and 7.7 % of the total, respectively. PFOA contributed an additional 6.0 %, and PFNA added 4.1 % to the total PFAS concentration.

Other species such as L-PFHxS (3.2 %), PFDA (2.4 %), and PFBA (2.3 %) were present in smaller but notable amounts. Less prevalent species included PFHpS (1.4 %), PFHpA (1.3 %), 9ClPF3ONS (1.3 %), whereas the rest accounted for less than 1 % of the total.

3.2.2. PFAS exposure by study group

Whilst the data analysis described above gives information on the exposure of the whole studied population to PFAS, we were also interested in determining if exposure was representative of the PFAS profile in the individual subgroups. We therefore analyzed these data considering the number and type detected in the three different subgroups, namely AD, MCI and HC. When this was done different frequencies of detection and concentration patterns were revealed for a number of PFAS species. In Fig. 3 characteristic ion chromatograms of serum samples from the three population groups analyzed in the study are shown.

As an example of these inter-group differences, PFPrS was detected in 79 % of the AD samples, but in only 10 % of the MCI and in 0 % of the HC samples. Similarly, PFHxA was detected in 57 % of AD patients, but only in 3 % of those demonstrating MCI and was absent from the serum the HC. PFBS was also detected in 31 % of AD, but only 5 % of the MCI and was not observed in HC. In all these cases, a much higher prevalence of these PFAS was observed in the AD patients in comparison to the other subject groups. Other, less dramatic, differences were seen between AD and the other groups exemplified by e.g., PFHpA which had a 91 % detection rate in AD compared to 73 % in HC and 70 % in MCI.

However, some PFAS were found at lower prevalence in the AD group compared to the other subjects. So PFHxS and L-PFHxS were found in only 88 % of AD patients, with their detection rates in HC and MCI at 95 % and 98 %, respectively. A similar trend was also observed for TFMS which was detected in only 5 % of the AD sera, whereas it was found in 93 % of the MCI and in 77 % of the HC samples. PFPrA was detected in 64 % of AD patients, but it was found in 100 % of both HC and MCI whilst PFDA had higher detection rates in HC (91 %) and MCI (90 %) compared to AD (77 %). These findings highlight again the added value of using a method suitable for the analysis of short chain PFAS.

A detailed overview of the percentage of samples in which the different PFAS species were detected across the three groups is provided in Table 1 which clearly shows that certain PFAS species were more prevalent in specific groups. In the AD subjects PFPrA was the most abundant individual component with a median value of 3.6 μ g/mL. The combined total for PFOS, both linear and branched chain species, gave a median value of 4.3 μ g/mL. For MCI and HC the same species were the most abundant. Greater median values were observed for PFPrA (26.0 and 23.1 μ g/mL for MCI and HC respectively). Lower values were observed for total PFOS of 2.2 and 2.1 μ g/mL for MCI and HC respectively. Overall median (and average) PFAS concentration values were higher in AD patients: 13 PFAS were found higher in AD vs HC group, whereas the reverse (HC > AD) occurred only for three PFAS species. A similar trend was observed when comparing AD with MCI: 14 PFAS exhibited AD>MCI; only for two was MCI higher than AD. A t-test was performed to get an indication of concentrations differentiations among the three groups. The t-test revealed some significant statistical differences among the species, as illustrated in Table 1. PFHpS, L-PFOS and br-PFOS showed significantly increased values in AD in relation to both MCI and HC with *p* values much lower than 0.05. Furthermore PFHxA, PFDA and L-PFHxS showed significantly different values when comparing AD with one of the other two groups. PFBS, PFPeS and br-PFHxS also gave low *p* values, however, they were not detected in a large proportion of the samples per group, therefore care must be taken when assigning significance to this observation. HC and MCI showed no statistically significant differences in their PFAS concentrations. Some examples of PFAS showing different distributions between the AD vs MCI and HC groups in their concentrations can be seen in the LC-MS profiles illustrated in Figs. 3 and in the box plots in Fig. 4.

As can be seen in Fig. 4, a number of individuals, representing significant outliers, were present within each of the groups, for example two outliers in the AD group with sum concentrations of 1037 and 717 ng/mL. From the metadata provided for each subject we determined

Fig. 2. Pie chart showing the contribution of different PFAS species to the total exposure per individual. Mean percentage has been calculated based on the mean concentrations of every PFAS to the sum concentration of all measured per individual.

Fig. 3. Profiles of the most abundant PFAS in the various study groups (AD, HC, MCI).

that that these outliers shared certain diets e.g., consumption of ω -3 lipids derived from fish, or health conditions (e.g., prostate cancer, leukemia). Such factors clearly cannot be disregarded as they could have influenced the serum PFAS concentrations to a great extent. However, the contribution of diet can be better evaluated only with the adoption of detailed and controlled nutritional intake records, which were not within the scope and the means of the current study.

As mentioned above, in most cases where differentiation was

observed between the groups, PFAS species were increased in AD subjects compared to the other two groups. We therefore examined the data to seek if these differences in PFAS profiles between AD and MCI could be related to age differences between the groups. Indeed, the Kruskal-Wallis test for continuous variables indicated that age was the only significant variable (p -value threshold 0.01). Other variables such as sex and BMI were investigated by applying the Chi-squared test for the categorical variable (Sex vs. Disease groups, BMI vs Disease groups) but

MCI_28_5425

Fig. 3. (continued).

no significant differences (p -value threshold 0.01) were observed (see Fig. 5).

It is also important, in the case of highly exposed subjects, to consider environmental exposure sources, such as contaminated drinking water. However, the studied population, which was living in the Thessaloniki area are not considered to be at high exposure as it is not in an industrial zone. Indeed, a study where these pollutants were measured in the drinking water of this area showed no detectable PFAS above the detection limits of the applied method (0.02–0.20 ng/L) [19]. However, there are no other publicly available data reporting significant PFOS/PFOA contamination in the city. A hypothesis could also be made that elderly people taking medications, or receiving medical treatment through blister packs, IV bags, tubing, coatings on pills or medical devices etc., that may contain PFAS-based surfactants are exposed to a higher extent to those compounds. Dietary sources of PFAS can also be a route for significant exposure to these chemicals.

To estimate the correlation of age with increased concentrations of specific PFAS the study samples were grouped into three age groups: <60, 60–75, and >75 years and comparisons were performed focusing on PFAS species that showed statistically significant differentiation based on clinical phenotypes (AD-HC, AD-MCI, HC-MCI). PFDA showed significant differentiation in the <60 vs. >75 comparison, while br-PFOS was significant in both the 60–75 vs. <60 and <60 vs. >75 comparisons. L-PFHxS and total PFHxS were significant in the <60 vs. >75 comparison, and total PFOS showed significance in both the 60–75 vs. <60 and <60 vs. >75 comparisons. L-PFOS was significant in the <60 vs. >75 comparison (see Supplementary Material Table S3). These findings indicate that specific PFAS species varied significantly with age, potentially influencing the observed clinical phenotypes.

As we have shown, LC-MS provides a rapid, sensitive, analytical technique for determining PFAS profiles in biofluids (such as serum/plasma/whole blood) [15,20,21] and UHPLC-MS/MS combined with 96 well plate-based micro SPE for sample clean up enables high sample throughput. Here, we aimed to screen serum for both long and ultra-short-chain PFAS. For this reason we selected a C18 phase for the analysis of long-chain PFAS and a stationary phase exhibiting both

hydrophobic and anion exchange characteristics to enhance retention of short-chain PFAS [22].

The methods described here allowed the rapid screening of blood from AD, MCI and HC groups for 30 long-chain PFAS and a further 6 ultra short PFAS species. Overall, we detected 33 PFAS compounds using these two methods. The results obtained in this study are in agreement with previous reports of the widespread presence of PFAS in human serum, with PFBA detected in all samples. High detection rates of PFNA, PFOA, linear PFHxS (L-PFHxS), linear PFOS (L-PFOS), and branched PFOS (br-PFOS) in over 90 % of samples highlight again that these compounds are widely distributed in the human population with PFPrA's significantly higher maximum concentration, and substantial contribution to total PFAS exposure, underscoring its environmental persistence and potential health risks.

However, an intriguing outcome of this limited study was the detection of significant differences in PFAS profiles between the AD and MCI patient groups. Thus, whilst the PFAS profiles of the MCI patients were somewhat similar to those of the HC group, those of the AD patients showed significant differences. The reason(s) for the differences found in PFAS profiles during the screening of these AD, MCI, and HC's serum samples are not clear. Whilst an association between PFAS and AD is an interesting possibility other factors such as e.g., age and diet cannot be discounted. Both our findings and the existing literature highlight that PFAS concentrations increase with age and can be associated with penetration of the blood-brain barrier integrity [11,12]. Age-related differences in PFAS exposures suggest that accumulation over time might be a critical factor, with older individuals exhibiting higher concentrations.

Particularly with regard to AD presentation, a recent publication has reported finding “a potential association” between PFAS in and perfluorooctanesulfonate in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) of AD patients [15]. Other studies, carried out in China and Japan, have also shown PFAS to be present in CSF [11,12,23,24], Whilst indicative, this preliminary study of PFAS in the CSF of patients with AD/cognitive impairment was, as the authors pointed out, based on a limited number of subjects ($n = 8$) and requires validation in a larger cohort [15].

Fig. 4. Box plot for four PFAS species (ng/mL) having different concentrations across the three groups of subjects examined.

Fig. 4. (continued).

Fig. 5. Box plots showing the distribution of age and BMI of the three groups of subjects.

Serum/plasma analysis of PFAS may represent a more straightforward screening option for widespread adoption compared to CSF, which is highly invasive and its sampling has more potential for side effects. Given that numerous methods for the analysis of PFAS in plasma/serum, in addition to those described here, have been developed (e.g., see [18,25–31] for some recent examples), validation of this possible association of PFAS with AD should not be too onerous. The present exploratory study, conducted using a relatively small number of subjects, has nevertheless provided the data that will enable the fine tuning, and full validation, of these rapid “fit for purpose” screening methods for routine PFAS analysis of the plasma of HC and neurological patients with MCI and AD.

4. Conclusions

The screening UHPLC-MS approaches described here enabled 137 blood serum samples comprising HC, MCI and AD patients to be rapidly analyzed for 30 long chain (and relatively non-polar) and 6 ultra short chain (polar) PFAS compounds. This analysis showed the presence of 33 of the selected analytes in serum, at a wide range of concentrations, whilst three species were not detected in any of the samples. Examination of the PFAS profiles revealed differences between the 3 population groups studied, with the profiles of the HC and MCI individuals being relatively similar, but those of the AD patients quite distinct. The reason (s) for the differences between the PFAS profiles of the AD patients remain unclear and may be also related to factors other than disease (e.g., age). This apparent correlation between AD and PFAS requires further investigation in order to confirm or disprove any relation between the two.

A key limitation of this preliminary study is the relatively small sample size, drawn from only two recruitment sites, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future research involving larger and more diverse, multi-centre cohorts will be essential to confirm and expand upon these results.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

O. Deda: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **S. Adams:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **M. Tsolaki:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **A. Lioupi:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **A.C. Tsolaki:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **G. Theodoridis:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **I.D. Wilson:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **R.S. Plumb:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Conceptualization. **H. Gika:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: O. Deda, M. Tsolaki, A. Lioupi, G. Theodoridis, and H. Gika report financial support provided by Horizon Europe. O. Deda, G. Theodoridis, H. Gika, A. Lioupi, and M. Tsolaki report a relationship with the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki Special Account for Research Funds that includes employment. S. Adams is a former employee of Waters Corp., and R.S. Plumb is an employee of Waters Corp. I.D. Wilson has in the past acted as a paid consultant to Waters and a number of other companies. The other authors declare no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. G. Theodoridis and I.D. Wilson are editors of the Journal of Chromatography B; to avoid conflicts of interest, the peer review of this article was managed independently by another editor and handled according to standard procedures.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021 Project 101079370, BiACEM: BiOMIC_AUTH, Center of Excellence in Metabolomics research.

This work was financially supported by project “Biomic_AUTH, Center of Excellence in Metabolomics research (BiACEM)” (Project number: 101079370), implemented under the Action “Horizon Europe Twinning grant”. The authors would like to thank Aristidis Koitsanos for his valuable assistance in improving the resolution and formatting of the figures and table.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2025.124738>.

Data availability

Due to ethical restrictions related to human participant data, the dataset is not publicly available but can be shared upon reasonable request and approval by the corresponding ethics committee.

References

- [1] G. Zheng, S.M. Eick, A. Salamova, Elevated levels of ultrashort- and short-chain Perfluoroalkyl acids in US homes and people, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 57 (2023) 15782–15793, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.2c06715>.
- [2] Biomonitoring Data Tables for Environmental Chemicals | CDC, (n.d.). http://www.cdc.gov/exposurereport/data_tables.html/ (accessed June 13, 2024).
- [3] European Human Biomonitoring Dashboard | VITO HBM, n.d. <https://hbm.vito.be/eu-hbm-dashboard> (accessed June 13, 2024).
- [4] D. Richterová, E. Govarts, L. Fábelová, K. Rausová, L. Rodriguez Martin, L. Gilles, S. Remy, A. Colles, L. Rambaud, M. Riou, C. Gabriel, D. Sarigiannis, S. Pedraza-Diaz, J.J. Ramos, T. Kosjek, J. Snoj Tratnik, S. Lignell, I. Gyllenhammar, C. Thomsen, L.S. Haug, M. Kolossa-Gehring, N. Vogel, C. Franken, N. Vanlarebeke, L. Bruckers, L. Stewart, O. Sepai, G. Schoeters, M. Uhl, A. Castaño, M. Esteban López, T. Göen, L. Palkovičová Murínová, PFAS levels and determinants of variability in exposure in European teenagers – results from the HBM4EU aligned studies (2014–2021), *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 247 (2023) 114057, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.114057>.
- [5] H. Canada, Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) in Canadians. <https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada/services/environmental-workplace-health/reports-publications/environmental-contaminants/human-biomonitoring-resources/per-polyfluoroalkyl-substances-canadians.html>, 2021 (accessed June 13, 2024).
- [6] Australian Government PFAS Taskforce | PFAS, (n.d.). <https://www.pfas.gov.au/> (accessed June 13, 2024).
- [7] Flemish Environment and Health Studies (FLEHS) | Departement, n.d.. <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/nl/flehs> (accessed June 13, 2024).
- [8] M. Ateia, A. Maroli, N. Tharayil, T. Karanfil, The overlooked short- and ultrashort-chain poly- and perfluorinated substances: a review, *Chemosphere* 220 (2019) 866–882, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.12.186>.
- [9] N.M. Brennan, A.T. Evans, M.K. Fritz, S.A. Peak, H.E. von Holst, Trends in the regulation of per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS): a scoping review, *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 18 (2021) 10900, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182010900>.
- [10] S. Brendel, É. Fetter, C. Staude, L. Vierke, A. Biegel-Engler, Short-chain perfluoroalkyl acids: environmental concerns and a regulatory strategy under REACH, *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 30 (2018) 9, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-018-0134-4>.
- [11] Y. Liu, X. Zhou, Y. Wu, X. Yang, Y. Wang, S. Li, X. Bai, D. Schlenk, W. Liu, Exposure and blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier permeability of PFASs in neonates, *Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett.* 9 (2022) 64–70, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.1c00862>.
- [12] W. Hu, M.-Y. Zhang, L.-Y. Liu, Z.-F. Zhang, Y. Guo, Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) crossing the blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier: their occurrence in human cerebrospinal fluid, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 442 (2023) 130003, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.130003>.
- [13] S. Lu, X. Zhu, P. Zeng, L. Hu, Y. Huang, X. Guo, Q. Chen, Y. Wang, L. Lai, A. Xue, Y. Wang, Z. Wang, W. Song, Q. Liu, G. Bian, J. Li, Q. Bu, X. Cen, Exposure to PFOA, PFOS, and PFHxS induces Alzheimer’s disease-like neuropathology in cerebral organoids, *Environ. Pollut.* 363 (2024) 125098, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2024.125098>.
- [14] V. Basaly, J. Hill, S.W. Bihaghi, E. Marques, A.L. Slitt, N.H. Zawia, Developmental Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) exposure as a potential risk factor for late-onset Alzheimer’s disease in CD-1 mice and SH-SY5Y cells, *Neurotoxicology* 86 (2021) 26–36, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2021.06.008>.
- [15] N. Delcourt, A.-M. Pouget, A. Grivaud, L. Nogueira, F. Larvor, P. Marchand, E. Schmidt, B. Le Bizet, First observations of a potential association between

- accumulation of per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances in the central nervous system and markers of Alzheimer's disease, *J. Gerontol. A Biol. Sci. Med. Sci.* 79 (2024) glad208, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glad208>.
- [16] E. Poptsi, D. Moraitou, E. Tsardoulis, A.L. Symeonidis, M. Tsolaki, R4Alz-R: a cutting-edge tool for spotting the very first and subtle signs of aging-related cognitive impairment with high accuracy, *Geroscience* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11357-024-01495-4>.
- [17] A. Jaus, C.F. Rime, J. Riou, B.J. Brüscheiler, M. Bochud, N. von Goetz, Serum biomonitoring of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) in the adult population of Switzerland: results from the pilot phase of the Swiss health study, *Environ. Int.* 198 (2025) 109382, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109382>.
- [18] B. Göckener, T. Weber, H. Rüdél, M. Bücking, M. Kolossa-Gehring, Human biomonitoring of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in German blood plasma samples from 1982 to 2019, *Environ. Int.* 145 (2020) 106123, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106123>.
- [19] E. Zafeiraki, D. Costopoulou, I. Vassiliadou, L. Leondiadis, E. Dassenakis, W. Traag, R.L.A.P. Hoogenboom, S.P.J. Van Leeuwen, Determination of perfluoroalkylated substances (PFASs) in drinking water from the Netherlands and Greece, *Food Addit. Contam. Part A Chem. Anal. Control Expo. Risk Assess.* 32 (2015) 2048–2057, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2015.1086823>.
- [20] R. Comito, E. Porru, F.S. Violante, Analytical methods employed in the identification and quantification of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in human matrices - a scoping review, *Chemosphere* 345 (2023) 140433, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.140433>.
- [21] K. Vorkamp, A. Castaño, J.-P. Antignac, L.D. Boada, E. Cequier, A. Covaci, M. Esteban López, L.S. Haug, M. Kasper-Sonnenberg, H.M. Koch, O. Pérez Luzardo, A. Osite, L. Rambaud, M.-T. Pinorini, G. Sabbioni, C. Thomsen, Biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods targeting human exposure to chemicals selected for a European human biomonitoring initiative, *Environ. Int.* 146 (2021) 106082, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106082>.
- [22] S.-H. Liang, J.A. Steimling, M. Chang, Analysis of ultrashort-chain and short-chain (C1 to C4) per- and polyfluorinated substances in potable and non-potable waters, *J. Chromatography Open* 4 (2023) 100098, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcoa.2023.100098>.
- [23] K.H. Harada, S. Hashida, T. Kaneko, K. Takenaka, M. Minata, K. Inoue, N. Saito, A. Koizumi, Biliary excretion and cerebrospinal fluid partition of perfluorooctanoate and perfluorooctane sulfonate in humans, *Environ. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 24 (2007) 134–139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2007.04.003>.
- [24] J. Wang, Y. Pan, Q. Cui, B. Yao, J. Wang, J. Dai, Penetration of PFASs across the blood cerebrospinal fluid barrier and its determinants in humans, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52 (2018) 13553–13561, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b04550>.
- [25] H.M. Starnes, K.D. Rock, T.W. Jackson, S.M. Belcher, A critical review and Meta-analysis of impacts of per- and Polyfluorinated substances on the brain and behavior, *Front Toxicol* 4 (2022) 881584, <https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2022.881584>.
- [26] S.F. Nakayama, T. Isobe, M. Iwai-Shimada, Y. Kobayashi, Y. Nishihama, Y. Taniguchi, M. Sekiyama, T. Michikawa, S. Yamazaki, H. Nitta, M. Oda, H. Mitsubuchi, M. Sanefuji, S. Ohga, N. Mise, A. Ikegami, R. Suga, M. Shimono, Poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances in maternal serum: method development and application in pilot study of the Japan Environment and children's study, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1618 (2020) 460933, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.460933>.
- [27] V. Marra, A. Abballe, E. Dellatte, N. Iacovella, A.M. Ingelido, E. De Felip, A simple and rapid method for quantitative HPLC MS/MS determination of selected Perfluorocarboxylic acids and Perfluorosulfonates in human serum, *Int. J. Anal. Chem.* 2020 (2020) 8878618, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8878618>.
- [28] Y. Ao, M. Nian, W. Tang, J. Zhang, Q. Zhang, J. Ao, A sensitive and robust method for the simultaneous determination of thirty-three legacy and emerging per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in human plasma and serum, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 415 (2023) 457–470, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-022-04426-4>.
- [29] G. Frigerio, S. Cafagna, E. Polledri, R. Mercadante, S. Fustinoni, Development and validation of an LC-MS/MS method for the quantitation of 30 legacy and emerging per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) in human plasma, including HFPO-DA, DONA, and cC6O4, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 414 (2022) 1259–1278, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-021-03762-1>.
- [30] L.M. Petrick, M.S. Wolff, D. Barupal, S.L. Teitelbaum, Comparison of untargeted and targeted perfluoroalkyl acids measured in adolescent girls, *Chemosphere* 290 (2022) 133303, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.133303>.
- [31] X. Gao, Y. Wang, D. Chen, J. Li, Y. Zhong, Y. Zhao, Y. Wu, On-line solid phase extraction-ultra high performance liquid chromatography-quadrupole/Orbitrap high resolution mass spectrometry determination of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in human serum, *J. Chromatogr. B* 1212 (2022) 123484, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2022.123484>.